

Model for Non-contact Blood Pressure Measurement Using the Facial Feature Amount based on Amplitude and Phase Analysis

Yu Kato, Kent Nagumo, Kosuke Oiwa, Akio Nozawa

Abstract: To monitor the daily blood pressure, developing a non-contact method for measuring blood pressure is necessary. In a previous study, we proposed a novel method that described the vascular structure of an entire human face as an electric circuit based on amplitude and phase analyses using visible and thermal images of the face. However, the model developed by that method did not consider the order of blood flow because the model applied at random the extracted features. In the present study, it considers a model that incorporates the order of blood flow utilizing amplitude and phase analyses. As a result, the estimated accuracy is improved by considering the order of blood flow. Higher accuracy requires more detailed vascular structure information of the face. It concluded that the facial feature, which is related to the blood pressure, can be obtained by the CEOF analysis.

Keywords: Blood pressure; CEOF analysis; Facial thermal image; Facial visible image

I. INTRODUCTION

Recently, the number of patients with lifestyle diseases has been increasing [1]. Lifestyle diseases account for approximately 60% of deaths [2], and this is a social issue. Hypertension is one of the main contributing factors to diseases due to lifestyle choices, and monitoring the blood pressure daily is expected to prevent or help control these diseases [3]. To measure blood pressure at home without stress, some methods that record the daily state of health have been developed [4] [5]. However, these methods are troublesome in that they require actions. For daily monitoring, developing a non-contact method to measure the blood pressure is necessary.

In a previous study, we proposed a novel method that developed a model that described the vascular structure of an entire face as an electric circuit based on amplitude and phase analyses using visible and thermal images of the face, and to estimate the blood pressure during a Valsalva maneuver [6]. However, the model developed by that method did not consider the order of blood flow because the model applied at random the extracted features obtained from the complex empirical orthonormal function (CEOF) analysis [7].

The objective of the present study is to develop a model is constructed that considered the order of blood flow using amplitude and phase analyses because the

model can reflect the detail vascular structure of the face. For generalization, the cold-pressor-test was carried out anew. The systolic blood pressure (SBP) and the visible and thermal images of an entire face were measured during the Valsalva maneuver or a cold-pressor-test, and the images were used in the CEOF analysis. Moreover, the facial feature regions were determined using the obtained images from the CEOF analysis, and a model that estimates the blood pressure was built considering the position of the blood based on the feature region.

II. METHODOLOGY

A. Experiment Approach

The measured physiological indexes were the following: the thermal and visible images containing the entire face and the SBP during the experiment. The bioinstrumentation system consisted of an infrared thermography (TVS-200EX; Avionics Co., Ltd), a smart phone (iPhone; Apple Inc.), and a non-invasive continuous blood hemomanometer (Finometer MIDI, Finapres Medical Systems BV). The size of the thermal images was 320×240 pixels, and the temperature resolution was less than 0.1 °C. The infrared emissivity of skin was $\varepsilon = 0.98$. The size of the visible images was 755×1334 pixels.

(a) Function of spatial amplitude (b) Function of spatial phase
 Fig. 1. Examples of function of spatial amplitude and phase

B. Procedure and Conditions

The human subjects were 22 years old in the Valsalva maneuver experiment and 29 years old in the cold-pressor-test experiment.

The Valsalva maneuver experiment consisted of four 1-min resting-state segments, (“Rest”) and three 20-s breath holdings (“Task”) Each Rest segment was given before and after a Task segment. In each Rest segment, the subject was instructed to sit in a rested state. In each Task segment, the subject was instructed to carry out breath holdings, which caused BP fluctuations. During the experiment, the subject’s eyes were closed.

The cold-pressor-test experiment consisted of four 2-min resting-state segments, (“Rest,”) which were given before and after the three 1-min cold-stimulus stage segments, (“Task.”) In each Rest segment, the subjects were instructed to sit at a resting state with their eyes closed. In each Task segment, the subjects were instructed to immerse their right hands in 14°C water contained in a constant-temperature water bath (NCB-2510, Tokyo Rikakikai Co., Ltd., Tokyo, Japan) with their eyes opened.

C. Indices for Analysis

The facial visible image obtained was converted from an RGB to YCbCr color scheme. The visible and facial thermal images were processed by a median filter (5 × 5 pixels), and the fluctuation of the face was corrected based on the start time of the experiment. Moreover, they were processed by a mosaic of average 5 × 5 pixels and the facial region was extracted; noises were removed by a low-pass filter (2 Hz, 12-dimensional Butterworth). The processed facial visible and thermal images were applied to obtain the

Fig. 2 Extracted facial features. Left images: result of the CEOF analysis. Right images: images converted into 5 × 5 pixels and positions of the facial features.

Fig. 3 Proposed model

amplitude and phase by CEOF analysis [7]. Figure 1 illustrates the example functions of spatial amplitude and phase by CEOF analysis. The following properties of each function are shown: the position where a signal appears in terms of spatial amplitude and direction of propagation in terms of spatial phase.

D. Construction of the model

The obtained visible and thermal images of the face were processed and used in the CEOF analysis. The size of the images was converted into 5 × 5 pixels to clearly show the facial features and to easily reflect the position of the blood. Fig. 2 shows a sample image of the CEOF analysis and the converted images. The converted images were divided into six groups (neck, eye, nose, forehead, cheek, and mouth), depending on the highest position of the features. In this study, images used to extract facial feature were phase function because it might show blood flow.

The obtained principal component from the facial visible images by the CEOF analysis was represented by current $I(t)$ and that from the thermal facial images was represented by electric charge $Q(t)$. Fig. 3 shows the proposed model, and the branch circuit that considered the separation of blood in the face [8]. To consider the blood position, the model was taken into account the order of blood flow based on the six groups depending on the facial features. This is attributed to that the first inflow and the final outflow of blood to the face is neck. The first step used the mode obtained from

Table.1 RMSE of each experiment

	Valsalva maneuver	Cold pressor test
RMSE(mmHg)	16.70	15.10

(a)Result of the Valsalva maneuver experiment

(b)Result of the cold-pressor-test experiment

Fig. 4 Comparison if measured and estimated SBP

the CEOF analysis which contained a feature of the neck as the highest principal component, and the third step used it as the next highest principal component. The second step used the mode that contained the features of the eye, forehead, cheek, and nose. However, if the nose could not be obtained, the mode that contained the mouth feature was used. Moreover, each facial part was used by each mode in each highest principal component. The calculated parameters were the resistance and capacitance. They were optimized by comparing the measured and estimated SBPs.

III. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Table.1 lists the root mean-squared error (RMSE) between the measured and estimated SBPs in each experiment. RMSE was smaller than in the case where the order of blood flow was not considered (the minimum RMSE was 17.571 mmHg) [6]. This is attributed to the model reflecting vascular structures more than the method not considering the order of blood flow. Thus, we concluded that more accurate blood-pressure estimates require that more detailed vascular structures are reflected.

Fig. 4 shows the graph that compares the measured SBP with the estimated SBP in each experiment. Both

estimated SBPs by the models partially followed the trend of the blood-pressure variability. However, the errors in the estimated SBP in the latter half appeared to be larger than those in the first half. We assumed that the capacitance contained in the model stored too much heat and thus improperly worked. Hence, the error of the estimated SBP increased at the latter half. We therefore suggest that a method must be developed to eliminate heat storage to reduce the error.

RMSE of result of cold-pressor-test experiment was as small as Valsalva maneuver experiment. Thus, this method was more general than before, we suggest, because it had the possibility of applying to some blood pressure fluctuation tests.

RMSE was smaller than in the case where the order of blood flow was not considered. Hence, we conclude that the facial feature, which is related to the blood pressure, can be obtained by the CEOF analysis because the accuracy of both models was improved by the reflected facial vascular structure.

Higher accuracy requires more detailed vascular structure information. Moreover, we suggest that a method must be developed to eliminate the stored heat to reduce the estimated SBP error.

IV. CONCLUSION

The objective of this study was to construct a model that considers the order of blood flow. It applied CEOF analysis to measured visible and thermal images of the entire face, and extracted facial features from each image. In addition, the electric circuit model was constructed using the facial features based on amplitude and phase obtained the analysis. As a result, the estimated accuracy was improved compared with that in the case where the order of blood flow was not considered and this method was more general than before we suggest. However, the errors in the estimated SBP in the latter half appeared to be larger than those in the first half. We conclude that the facial feature, which is related to the blood pressure, can be obtained by CEOF analysis. Higher accuracy requires more detailed vascular structure information. Moreover, we suggest that a method must be developed to eliminate the stored heat to reduce the estimated SBP error.

ACKNOWLEDGMENT

This work was partially supported by Aoyama Gakuin University-Supported Program “Early Eagle Program.”

REFERENCES

- [1] Ministry of Education, Culture, Sports, Science and Technology, Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare, and Ministry of Agriculture, Forestry and Fisheries: "Explanation of diet guidelines," Available at: (<http://www.maff.go.jp/j/syokuiku/attach/pdf/shishinn-5.pdf>) [Accessed 6 December 2019]
- [2] Ministry of Health, Labour and Welfare Insurance Bureau Medical Care Collaboration Policy Section Data Health / Medical Cost Optimization Measures Promotion Office: "I. Latest Trends in Lifestyle Disease Control Measures – Direction of Specific Health Checkup / Specific Health Guidance Project (Third Phase)," Available at: (<https://www.niph.go.jp/soshiki/jinzai/koroshoshiryo/tokutei29/keikaku/program/K1-1.pdf>) [Accessed 6 December 2019]
- [3] L. Halme, R. Vesalainen, M. Kaaja, and I. Kantola: "Self-monitoring of blood pressure promotes achievement of blood pressure target in primary health care," *American Journal of Hypertens*, Vol.18, No.11, pp.1415-1420 (2005)
- [4] Y. Kato, M. Imura, Y. Kuroda, O. Osamu, and M. nambu: "Basic Study for Realization of Healthcare Device by Measurement of Cardiovascular Physiological Information from Sole," *Journal of Medical and Biological Engineering*, Vol.50, No.1, pp.23-30 (2012) (in Japanese)
- [5] S. Tanaka, K. Motoi, M. Nogawa, T. Yamakosi, and K. Yamakosi: "Development of a Blood Pressure Monitoring System Installed in a Toilet Seat for Use in Home Healthcare," *Journal of Medical and Biological Engineering*, Vol.44, No.3, pp.467-474 (2006) (in Japanese)
- [6] Y. Kato, K. Nagumo, S Bando, K Oiwa, and A. Nozawa: "Electric Circuit Model and Thermo-Hue Hemodynamic Analysis for Non-Contact Blood Pressure Measurement," *Journal of the Institute of Electrical Engineers of Japan (Transactions on Electronics, and Information Systems)*, Vol.140, No.1 (in printing)
- [7] R. Kawamura: "A space-time data analysis using complex empirical orthogonal functions," *Geographical Review of Japan Ser. A*, Vol.62, No.11, pp.812-822 (1989) (in Japanese)
- [8] K. Suzuki, and A. Inamori: "MYSTERIES OF THE HUMAN BODY -Circulatory Organs, Blood and Immune System-," Maruzen Inc., Japan (2005) (in Japanese)